

Critical implementation risks and mitigation actions

Foreseen Risks

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<i>The table shows the risks already listed in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement (read-only).</i>			
Risk No	Description	Work Package No(s)	Proposed Mitigation Measures
1	Partners are not able to finish their prototypes and designs before the scheduled events	WP2	Medium – one of the criteria for the selection of garments to go onto the fashion collections will be the availability of finished pieces on time
2	Pieces of the fashion collection do not follow the sustainability standards	WP2	Medium – constant checks will be performed by the design leaders, reviewing the sketches and mediums for each design. The selection of pieces of fashion will be shared with the rest of partners.
3	A reduced number of sustainable fashion designs is available for selection	WP2	Low – if partners cannot reach the development of 10-15 sustainable pieces, they will select and present the number they can reach. If it is lower than 6, alternative artists and sustainable designers will be contacted for their participation
4	Designs developed do not fit the models correctly	WP2,WP4	Low – constant reviews will be carried out by design leaders and design fitting will be performed in advance
5	Technical problems during the performance (restricted use of drones, low battery on the devices, bad quality WiFi, incorrect hanging of lights and projectors, microphone feedback, etc.)	WP4,WP3	Medium – events will be planned well in advance considering the space design plans and the installation of all the devices will be arranged at least one day before the show takes place. Sound, lights and other checks will be carried out with the technicians prior to the event.
6	The digital strategies do not adapt well to the event location/concept, or difficult the visibility	WP4,WP3	Medium – videomapping, lighting, LED walls and temporary architecture strategies will be designed according to the fashion designs and considering the space architectural plans, including details of walls, light sources, measures, etc. Progress will be monitored by specialized teams on location.
7	Models can't dance for the performance and urban dances planned	WP4	Low – models will be sent the choreography steps in advance for them to practice before and the choreographer will have a live session with them prior to the event to correct potential errors

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8	Low attendance in roundtables	WP4	Low - Roundtables and conferences will be announced with time and will focus on attractive and actual topics to raise the interest of the audience
9	Aesthetics in the events do not follow the same patterns	WP4	Low – make up and hairdressing will be design jointly by all partners according to the artistic direction and the choreographer insights.
10	New sanitary emergency situation that restricts live events	WP1	High – the events will be transformed into digital events via streaming tools
11	Flights' prices increase	WP1	High – online meetings will be held whenever needed, and dates for the events will be fixed with enough anticipation, so that partners can book their trips in advance

Unforeseen Risks

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Risk No	Description	Work Package No(s)	Proposed Mitigation Measures
U 1	Partner responsible for digital engagement strategy design and implementation, and communications leads decides to withdraw from the project a few months before the events are to take place.	WP3,WP6	Partners will implement conflict resolution measures, and if they fail they will reorganize the work plan, redistribute the partner's remaining budget and tasks, and rework the original project proposal to submit an amendment which would guarantee that the original work plan was delivered.

State of play

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<i>Continuous Reporting (Critical Risks screen) - Give the state of play of the risks that were identified in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement (and new risks that materialised during project implementation) and add new mitigation measures, if needed.</i>				
Risk No	Period	Did you apply risk mitigation measures?	Did your risk materialise?	Comments
1	1	Yes	No	Partners took care in establishing realistic dates for the performance runway shows to be held, allowing for sufficient time for the collections to be properly developed.
2	1	Yes	No	Every collection was monitored by a team of sustainability experts who documented the entire sustainable fashion development process to ensure that meaningful improvements were being made to achieve new sustainable fashion design and production methods
3	1	Yes	No	Partners agreed on developing a large base of designs, both through student and contestant's participation, to allow for final editing and selection of the best and most representative designs to be showcased onto both the portfolios and the runway shows.
4	1	Yes	No	All designs were developed according to a standard size guide. Regular quality checks were performed to ensure that the designs followed the intended measurements. Moreover, casting and fitting was directed to find models with the right measurements for each garment.
5	1	Yes	Yes	Creamodite experienced some technical difficulties during the roundtables presentations, because the laser pointer which would be used to switch slides during the presentation was not functioning properly. It was quickly and efficiently solved by coordinating certain subtle hand-gestures for the audio-visual crew to change slides from the sound operation area.

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6	1	Yes	No	When WP3 tasks were reallocated so that each partner would oversee their own, local teams were able to conveniently access the location regularly and whenever needed. In addition, tests were performed in advance to ensure that the digital strategy would adapt well to the location. As a result, all digital engagement strategies were executed properly during the events.
7	1	Yes	No	All choreography was planned to take into account the skills and limitations of performers; hence, where a dance choreography was to be put in place (such as Creamodite and Uminho's show), actual dancers were procured; and the model's choreography in all cases was designed, planned and rehearsed to be equal parts effective in creating a performance and easy to execute.
8	1	Yes	Yes	Even though engaging local personalities and sustainability experts were secured as guest speakers, and the events were announced and promoted in advance; the turnout at the roundtables was not as good as for the performance runway events. Thankfully, the roundtables were recorded, so the content will be edited and disseminated in short videos during year 2 of the project, in the project website and social media, to raise awareness about the important discussions held.
9	1	Yes	Yes	Each partner was tempted to design hair and make up tailored to suit their collection's particular aesthetic, however, planning meetings were held to coordinate aesthetics

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				that would match each partner's collections whilst following a common aesthetic.
10	1	Yes	No	Fortunately, across the EU no new sanitary emergencies were declared during the months where the events took place (May to July 2023). Nonetheless, the shows were planned to include live-streaming services to increase the visibility of the activities performed and allow for last-minute sanitary emergency mitigation strategies.
11	1	Yes	Yes	2022 and 2023 did indeed see an increase in flight prices as a consequence of rising petrol prices. For this reason, and in-keeping with the project's commitment to sustainability, only essential travel was planned and booked in advance, to visit and assess the locations where the events would take place to design the digital engagement strategy; and for at least one partner from each team to attend each other's events.
U1	1	Yes	Yes	Xsentrik Arts, partner responsible for the design and implementation of digital engagement strategies (WP3) as well as project communications and dissemination lead (WP6), withdrew from the project only a few months before the events would take place. To mitigate the risk, partners absorbed the digital engagement strategy design and production for their own events: - Creamodite, whose main runway event was programmed for May 19, adjusted the original concept for a futuristic videomapping design to an intricate lightshow, which would deliver the same aesthetic results whilst requiring less development time than a

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				videomapping animation. - Uminho, also time-constricted due to their show being planned for June 2nd, adapted the plan originally formulated with Xsentrik Arts – which contemplated creating ephemeral architecture in the form of fabric panels to project the videomapping onto in the runway, to an LED wall which would project concept videos, aided by ephemeral architecture installations on the floor mimicking textile waste piles, based on their collection's inspiration. - Unicompania was able to secure a local videomapping animation and production team, with which they collaborated to create a digital engagement strategy to intervene their selected location during their runway performance event, which took place on July 4th . Moreover, Creamodite took over Xsentrik Art's WP6 responsibilities, creating content and managing the project social media and website, as well as overseeing the project's communications and dissemination plan.